

THE ISSUE OF IMAGE AND IMAGE IN FICTION

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Abstract: The article examines the role of image and imagery in fiction, its genesis and theoretical foundations.

Keywords: image, imagery, means of artistic representation, theoretical foundations, genesis

BADIIY ADABIYOTDA OBRAZ VA OBRAZLILIK MASALASI

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O'zbek tili va adabiyoti kafedrasida o'qituvchisi

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada tasvir va tasvirning badiiy adabiyotdagi o'rni, uning genezisi va nazariy asoslari ko'rib chiqiladi

Калит сўзлар: образ, образлилик, бадий тасвир воситалари, назарий асослар, генезис

ПРОБЛЕМА ОБРАЗА И ОБРАЗА В ХУДОЖЕСТВЕ

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Аннотация: В статье рассматривается роль образа и образности в художественной литературе, его генезис и теоретические основы

Ключевые слова: образ, образность, средства художественного изображения, теоретические основы, генезис

Literature is an art of words, it is directly expressed through various images. It is better to start the study of the nature of the artistic image with the meaning of the term. The term "Образ"(image) is derived from the word "raz" (line), from the word "raz" "razit" (to draw, cut, carve) and from it "obrazit" (draw, carve, to make a shape). From "Image" came "image" ("taken in general"). The term image was first mentioned in Aristotle's Poetics.

About the image VG Belinsky "... There is nothing random in it. All parts are subordinated to the idol, all are focused on one goal, all in unity create one beauty, integrity and individuality, so we are this man Yusufbek Haji, this man Qori Ishkamba, this girl Layli, this guy Majnun we say. Each of them is "more generous than any event, more reliable than any history, which summarizes the essence of certain events in reality." In fact, because the image is focused on one goal, we call the images in the work as mentioned above. This makes it easier for the reader to think.

VG Belinsky says that the term image is not only used in art, but also in philosophy that it is customary to understand life as an image of the human mind, to separate their essence and ideas from the facts of science and reality. Focuses on the image in science and how to distinguish it. An event is not just an appearance, but serves to express the most typical of these scenes (exemplary, the most valuable example), it is a visual (illustrative) image. Of course, in its essence it has a typical character (generalization), but it does not exaggerate the facts. In life, the term "image" is used in another sense, it can be called a photographic image. The image captures and continues to capture the hearts of millions with its beauty and impact. It becomes, as VG Belinsky puts it, "the beating heart of human life, its blood and

soul, its light and sun." Because the image, with its vivid movement, charm, brightness, deeply embodies the legitimacy of events. Hotam Umurov also states the following about the image of art in the textbook "Literary Theory": In the science of literature, "image" means not only the events reflected in the human mind, but also the life that is understood, processed (recut) and described by the artist through words. As H. Umurov rightly points out, the image is the symbol of art, of fiction. Therefore, from the smallest detail in the work to the largest image, it is used to achieve a specific goal.

Literary critic Erkin Khudoiberdiyev, in contrast to H. Umurov's views on the image, states the following about the image and its importance: "The figurative representation of reality is one of the main features of literature and art. Figurative reflection requires general, legitimate aspects of life in individuals, events, and certain emotions. Of course, such complex representations of the figurative image did not appear suddenly. It is the product of a long historical development. Due to the great achievements of the development of human thought, the disclosure of the most important and typical aspects of reality, the essence of events in the "life form" has become one of the main features of truly artistic images. In fact, it is no exaggeration to say that the image is a means of shaping the literature, especially fiction, in the mind and consciousness of the reader who creates it, and at the heart of it expands his views and opinions on life. E. Khudoyberdiyev gave detailed information about the important and relevant features of the image. The scientist also notes that the image has special features. "So let's talk about the types of images and their characteristics. The first characteristic of an artistic image is its richness of vividness and accuracy, which determines the power of the emotional impact of art and literature on people. The second characteristic of the image is that it is at the same time clear. , combines common, typical features together without repetition. Only when the image is vivid and clear will it affect people quickly. " He noted that the image, in addition to being vivid and vivid, embodies general, typical features

that are not clearly repeated at the same time, and that the image can quickly affect people only when it has such features. advanced the idea.

In fact, the "image" is typical of the Slavic languages, it represents an imaginary scene of events. When the Slavs used the word "image", they meant, first of all, the image of Jesus Christ (Jesus), sent by God to save mankind from suffering, depicted by artists and sculptors.

The conclusion is that literature includes everything in life (man, thing, animal, event, object, plant; words, phrases, lexical resources, means of expression - exaggeration, reduction, khashatish, amonim, synonyms, antonyms; anaphora, epiphora, etc.) is the law.

References

1. Oripova, G. (2019). UZBEK POETRY AND THE WORLD LITERATURE IN THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE. *Scientific Journal of Polonia University*, 32(1), 116-120.
2. Oripova Gulnoza Murodilovna. (2019). THE PECULIARITIES OF VAZN METER IN UZBEK POETRY OF THE INDEPENDENCE PERIOD. *International Journal of Anglisticum. Literature, Linguistics and Interdisciplinary Studies*. Volume: 8 /Issue:2/. – Macedonia, 2019. –P.33-39.
3. Murodilovna, O. G. (2020). Melody and musicality in Lirycs. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(11), 656-664.
4. Oripova G. M., Tolibova M. T. Q. Composition Of Modern Uzbek Stories //The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations. – 2021. – T. 3. – №. 03. – C. 245-249.
5. Oripova, G. (2020, December). RHYTHM AND MYTHING IN LYRICAL GENRE. In *Конференции*.

6. Oripova, G. (2019) "Traditions of folk ballads and distinctiveness of uzbek poetry of independence period," *Scientific journal of the Fergana State University*: Vol. 2 , Article 12.
7. Oripova, G. M. (2021). Genesis And Essence Of Genre Concept. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 3(12), 90-94.
8. Sabirdinov, A. (2019). Sketches to the novel "Night and day" by Chulpan. *Scientific journal of the Fergana State University*, 1(6), 119-120.
9. Sabirdinov, A. G. (2021). Interpretation of Characters in Utkir Hoshimov's Story "Yanga". *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding*, 8(6), 196-200.
10. Sabirdinov, A. (2020, December). ASKAR KASIMOV IN THE UZBEK POETRY OF THE XX CENTURY THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF CREATION. In Конференции.
11. Sabirdinov, A. G. (2021). Interpretation of the banned period in the stories of Naim Karimov. *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research*, 10(11), 4-91.
12. Сабирдинов, А. Г. (1993). Слово и образ в поэзии Айбека.
13. kizi Yunusaliyeva, G. A. (2021). CHARACTER CREATION ABILITY OF ERKIN A'ZAM.
14. Khallokova, M. E. (2018). Important Aspects of Establishing Non-State Educational Institutions. *Eastern European Scientific Journal*, (2).
15. Ergashevna, K. M. (2021). Factors for improving the quality of education in primary schools of non-state educational institutions. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(9), 792-796.
16. Халлокова, М. (2022). Нодавлат таълим муассасаларида таълим тизимини модернизациялаш. *Общество и инновации*, 3(1), 151-157.
17. Oybek Barziyev. (2021) Traditional Poetic Series Related to Detail Motivating to Enlightenment. *International Journal on Integrated Education*. 4(12).
18. Barziev, O. (2021). LYRICAL INTERPRETATION OF "I" IN THE POETRY

OF ANBAR OTIN, DILSHODI BARNO AND SAMAR BONU. CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES (2767-3758), 2(06), 61-66.

19. Barziyev Oybek. THE DESCRIPTION OF NATIONALITY IN UZBEK POETRY IN THE PERIOD OF LATE XIXth CENTURIES AND EARLY XXth CENTURIES. Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University, 2021, P. - 3314-321.